

the products were established as **4** from a critical analysis of their ^1H NMR spectral data. A probable mechanism for the formation of **4** is given in Scheme 1.

flavanone gave a new type of interesting products which could be converted to a variety of benzopyran fused polycycles.

Scheme 1

The product **4** possesses a diene moiety and so we studied its Diels-Alder reaction with *N*-phenylmaleimide in anticipation that this reaction would produce a new type of benzopyrone derivatives. Thus, when a mixture of **4a** (the reduction product of **3** in methanol) and *N*-phenylmaleimide was heated in refluxing toluene, the starting diene disappeared after 8 h. Examination of the concentrate of the reaction mixture by TLC showed the formation of three major products. Attempted resolution of

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr disc on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3 on a Bruker AM-300L (300 MHz), Varian Unity Plus (U+) (400 MHz) and mass spectrum on a JEOL D-300 spectrometer.

*General procedure for NaBH_4 reduction of *E*-3-cinnamylidene flavanone :*

To a solution of *E*-3-cinnamylidene flavanone (200 mg) in anhydrous methanol or ethanol excess sodium borohydride was added gradually and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 h. It was then diluted with water, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with chloroform. The residue obtained after removal of chloroform was chromatographed over silica gel to get the product.

The ^1H NMR spectral data of **4a** and **4b** were as follows :

4a : Yield : 45%; m.p. 114–120 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz) : δ 3.17 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.60 (1H, d, J 6.7 Hz), 5.54 (1H, dd, J 16.2 and 6.7 Hz), 5.99 (1H, s), 6.31 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 6.59 (1H, s), 6.65 (1H, br. d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 6.79 (1H, br. t, J 8.1 Hz, Ar-H) and 6.95–7.34 (12H, m, Ar-H) for the major isomer. The presence of the minor isomer was evident from the appearance of small peaks at δ 3.23 (s, OCH_3), 4.73 (d, J 6.5 Hz), 5.55 (dd, J 16.2 and 6.5 Hz), 6.01 (s), 6.39 (d, J 16.2 Hz) and 6.61 (s). Some other peaks of the minor component overlapped with those of the major one; EIMS : m/z 354 (M^+).

4b : Yield : 35%; m.p. 92–97 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz) : δ 1.13 (3H, t, J 6.9 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 3.36 (2H, q, J 6.9 Hz, $\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 4.78 (1H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 5.63 (1H, dd, J 16.2 and 6.6 Hz), 6.06 (1H, s), 6.33 (1H, d, J

- 4**
 a . R = Me
 b . R = Et

the components of the concentrate by chromatography over silica gel afforded only one product in low yield (22%). The other products were possibly destroyed during chromatography. The isolated product has been assigned the gross structure **5** from its analytical and spectral data. The configuration of this cycloaddition product containing six stereogenic centres, however, remains unsettled.

5

Thus, borohydride reduction of *E*-3-cinnamylidene-

16.2 Hz), 6.64 (1H, s), 6.72 (1H, br. d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 6.83 (1H, br. t, J 8.1 Hz, Ar-H) and 7.01–7.44 (12H, m, Ar-H) for the major isomer. The minor isomer showed the following small peaks at δ 1.19 (t, J 6.9 Hz), 6.46 (d, J 16.2 Hz) and 6.67 (s).

Diels-Alder reaction of 4a and N-phenylmaleimide :

The diene **4a** (1 mmol) and *N*-phenylmaleimide (1 mmol) were taken in distilled toluene (15 ml) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 8 h. Then toluene was removed *in vacuo* and the crude material was chromatographed over silica gel to get the Diels-Alder adduct **5**.

The analytical and spectral data of **5** were as follows.

5 : m.p. 138–139 °C; IR : 1760 (C=O) and 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (400 MHz) : δ 2.87 (1H, m), 3.29 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.69 (1H, br. d, J 8.84 Hz), 3.82 (1H, dd, J 8.8 and 6.8 Hz), 4.07 (1H, dd, J 8.4 and 6.0 Hz),

4.89 (1H, d, J 10.8 Hz), 5.26 (1H, br. peak), 5.34 (1H, br. s) and 6.91–7.43 (19 H, m, Ar-H); EIMS : m/z 527 (M^+) (Found : C, 79.11; H, 5.37; N, 2.39. $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 79.68; H, 5.54; N, 2.65%).

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